

Association Between Maternal Literacy and Employment, and Nutritional status of under Fives in Comprehensive Health Centre, Dadin Kowa, Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Background: Malnutrition accounts for about 45% of deaths among under five children worldwide thus posing a major public health challenge especially in low-resource settings like Nigeria, where poverty, food insecurity, and poor feeding practices increase the risk of being malnourished. This study aimed to determine the influence of maternal literacy and employment on nutritional status of children aged less than five years in Comprehensive Health Centre, Dadin Kowa, Jos, Plateau State.

Methods: A cross sectional analytical study was carried out on two hundred and fifty children under five (125 from working mothers, 125 from non-working mothers) and were assessed to determine the influence of maternal literacy and employment on their nutritional status. Data was collected via interviewer-administered questionnaire and anthropometric measurements and were analyzed using SPSS version 25 ($p < 0.05$). Multivariable logistic regression was used to estimate adjusted odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for malnutrition.

Results: Non-working mothers were younger (26.8 ± 5.1 vs 30.0 ± 5.6 years) and less educated (12.8% no formal education vs 0% working mothers; 16.0% vs 36.8% had tertiary education). Children of non-working mothers had higher rates of underweight (16.8% vs 11.2%), stunting (12.8% vs 7.2%), and wasting (20.8% vs 13.6%). Maternal education showed a strong graded protective effect, with no formal and primary education being significantly associated with increased odds of malnutrition (all $p < 0.05$), whereas secondary education was not significant.

Conclusion: Maternal employment alone was not significantly associated with reducing malnutrition rather higher maternal education has a stronger protective effect against malnutrition.

Keywords: Nutritional status, under-five children, maternal employment, maternal literacy.

Introduction

The World Health Organization has shown that malnutrition accounts for about 45% of deaths among under five children worldwide thus posing a major public health challenge¹ especially in low-resource settings like Nigeria, where poverty, food insecurity, and poor feeding practices increase the risk of being malnourished. Data from the National Bureau of Statistics² have highlighted that there is rising female labour participation which is a good development as, maternal employment may boost household resources for nutrition though research has shown it also reduces time for breastfeeding and complimentary feeding practices particularly in informal sectors.^{3,4} Conversely, non-working mothers may offer more caregiving time but they face barriers like low education and income which hinder optimal child nutrition.^{5,6} These dynamics create a complex interplay, with mixed evidence: National Demographic Health Survey data⁷ show employed mothers with secondary & tertiary education are linked to lower underweight odds, but time constraints may elevate wasting as demonstrated by research in urban areas.⁵

In Plateau State, stunting (46.4%) and wasting (4.8%) rates among under-five children exceed national averages, driven by adolescent motherhood and suboptimal feeding in areas like Mangu LGA (stunting: 29.5%, wasting: 12%).^{7,8} Yet, local evidence is sparse as no comparative studies examine maternal employment and literacy's combined effects in places like Jos South Local Government Area, despite the preponderance of sub-urban poverty and diverse livelihoods.⁹ Recent national surveys highlight gaps in complementary feeding,¹⁰ but Plateau-specific data on working vs non-working mothers remain absent, limiting targeted interventions. This study addressed these gaps by comparing nutritional outcomes in Dadin Kowa, hypothesizing that children of working mothers with higher literacy exhibit better nutritional status than those of non-working mothers with lower literacy, which is as a result of better resources and feeding practices. Thus, this study aimed to find out the influence of maternal literacy and employment on nutritional status of these children as findings from this study would guide

local nutritional policies, provide knowledge on child health and provide data for other researchers in this field.

Methodology

Study area

The study was conducted in Dadin Kowa community of Jos South Local Government Area (LGA), Plateau State, Nigeria. The community has an estimated population of 45,824, with about 22,544 women of reproductive age and 4,344 children under the age of 5 years in 2020.¹¹ Dadin Kowa is a sub-urban community with parts being an urban slum. The population is predominantly Muslim, with Hausa, Fulani, and other tribes (Jukun, Jarawa, Ebira, Sayawa, Alago) working mostly in civil service, artisanship, farming, or self-employment. Social amenities like schools, power supply, potable water, and roads are good, while housing and waterways are fairly adequate. The literacy level is lower than the national average, and most residents are of lower socio-economic status. Three hospitals serve Dadin Kowa community, including two private and one public (Comprehensive Health Center), where this research was conducted.

Study population and eligibility criteria

Mothers of children under five years attending the clinic at Comprehensive Health Center Dadin Kowa and their children were studied. Biological mothers who were permanent residents of Dadin Kowa were included, while those with chronic illness were excluded due to unreliable nutritional information. Also, children with chronic illnesses, congenital anomalies, or preterm birth (<37 weeks) were excluded to avoid distortion of anthropometric measurements.

Study design and sample size determination

A cross-sectional analytical study design was used to compare nutritional status of under five children between working and non-working mothers. Sample size was calculated using the formula for detecting a difference in a binary outcome (stunting) between two independent groups in logistic/cross-sectional studies by Hsieh et al¹²:

$$n \text{ per group} = [(Z_{\alpha/2} + Z\beta)^2 \times \{p(1-p) + p(1-p)\}] / (p_1 - p_2)^2$$

where:

$$Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96 (\alpha = 0.05, \text{two-sided})$$

$Z_{\beta} = 0.84$ (80% power)

$p =$ expected stunting prevalence in children of non-working mothers = 0.38¹³

$p =$ expected stunting prevalence in children of working mothers = 0.23¹⁴

This yielded $n = 125$ participants per group.

Sampling Technique

Dadin Kowa ward was purposively selected from 20 wards in Jos South LGA due to its sub-urban nature, proximity, and peaceful environment. The Comprehensive Health Center was chosen as the largest health facility offering daily maternal and child health services in the community. On routine immunization days, eligible mothers were consecutively recruited into the study and were stratified by employment status into working and non-working groups until a sample size of 125 per group was reached.

Data collection

Community entry involved meeting gatekeepers to discuss research aims and mobilize mothers for immunization days. Three research assistants were trained on the study protocol (inter-observer reliability >90% for anthropometrics). On data collection days, respondents were briefed, and verbal informed consent was obtained, ensuring confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation. Data were collected over two months using the ODK data collection kit.

Data Tools

A pretested questionnaire adapted from USAID/FAO¹⁵ was used to collect data on socio-demographics, child data, weaning and anthropometrics. Weight was estimated via a calibrated digital scale (mother alone, then with child; to the nearest 0.1 kg); height/length was obtained using a height board (<2 years) or stadiometer/tape (>2 years, due to limitations; to the nearest 0.1 cm). The 2006 WHO Child Growth Standards were used, defining underweight (WAZ < -2SD), stunting (HAZ < -2SD), and wasting (WHZ < -2SD) as malnutrition indicators.¹⁶

Definition of variables

- Non-working mother: a woman who stays at home, she may or may not be educated and she may or may not be financially independent.
- Working Mother: defined as a woman with the ability to combine a career with the added responsibility of raising a child. Within this broad term are encompassed two different categories of working women: stay at home with a remote job and the woman who works away from home while managing to fulfill her maternal duties

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS statistics version 25. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant, with Fishers exact test used for expected cell count < 5 and chi-square test for expected cell count >5. Multivariable logistic regression estimated adjusted Odds Ratios/Confidence Intervals (AORs/Cis) for malnutrition by employment/literacy, controlling for maternal age, number of children and education.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Plateau State Hospitals Management Board Ethics Committee (ref no. HMB/ADM/772/1/108). Verbal informed consent was secured after explaining the study's aims, ensuring voluntary participation, confidentiality, and anonymity, with the option to withdraw without consequences.

Results

Respondents' sociodemographic factors

The study interviewed 125 working mothers with the mean age of 30.0±5.6 years and 125 non working mothers with the mean age of 26.8±5.1 years. The difference in mean age was statistically significant with $p < 0.001$. Most of the mothers were married ($p = 0.156$) and Hausa/Muslim ($p < 0.01$ and $p = 0.015$ respectively). Majority of the working mothers completed tertiary education and were older (26-30 years) as compared to the non-working mothers who mostly completed secondary school and were

younger (18-25 years). Both factors were statistically significant with $p < 0.01$ as shown in Table 1.

Among the children assessed, i.e., 125 children for both groups of mothers, non-working mothers had 58 (46.4%) females and 67 (53.6%) males, while working mothers had 51 (40.8%) females and 74 (59.2%) males ($p = 0.258$). Non-working mothers' children were mostly younger (0–23 months: 58.4%) compared to working mothers (42.4%; $p = 0.001$; Table 2).

Association between maternal employment status and child nutrition status

Compared with non-working mothers (reference group), the odds of having children under five with normal weight for age among working mothers was 0.59 times that of non-working mothers (OR=0.59, 95% CI: 0.03-1.29, $P = 0.241$). Similarly, the odds of having under-fives with normal height for age among working mothers was 0.53 times that of non-working mothers (OR=0.53, 95% CI: 0.23-1.25, $P = 0.121$), while the odds of having children with normal weight for height was 0.60 times that of non-working mothers (OR=0.60, 95% CI: 0.32-1.14, $P = 0.1118$). None of the associations were statistically significant after adjustment for maternal age, maternal education, number of children and household income as shown on Table 3.

Association between maternal education and child malnutrition among working and nonworking mothers

Among working mothers, maternal education was significantly associated with the nutritional status of under-five children after adjustment for maternal age, child age, number of children, and household income. Using mothers with tertiary education as the reference category, the odds of having under-five children with underweight was 5.7 times, stunting 13.1 times and wasting 4.6 times among those with only primary education compared to those with tertiary education (AOR = 5.7, 95% CI: 1.4-23.1, $P = 0.015$), (AOR = 13.1, 95% CI: 1.5-113.2, $p = 0.019$) and (AOR = 4.6, 95% CI: 1.5–14.3, $p = 0.008$), respectively. Table 4A.

In Table 4B, non-working mothers with no formal education had 13.2 times the odds of having

underweight children, 27.8 times the odds of having stunted children and 10.1 times the odds of having wasted children compared with non-working mothers with tertiary education (AOR = 13.2, CI: 2.9-60.4, $p = 0.001$), (AOR = 27.8, CI: 3.0-259.1, $p = 0.004$) and (AOR = 10.1, 95% CI: 2.8-36.1, $p < 0.001$) respectively. Similarly, nonworking mothers with primary education also had significantly higher odds of having children who were underweight and those with wasting which were 5.7 and 4.6-times higher respectively compared to those with tertiary education after Bonferroni's correction. No statistically significant differences were observed among nonworking mothers with secondary education only.

Table 1: Socio demographic characteristics of mothers

Variable	NWM (%) n=125	WM (%) n=125	χ^2	p-value
RELIGION				
			5.896	0.015
Islam	109 (87.2)	94 (75.2)		
Christian	16 (12.8)	31 (24.8)		
ETHNIC GROUP				
			51.895	< 0.01*
Hausa	63 (50.4)	66 (52.8)		
Igbo	1 (0.8)	0 (0.00)		
Yoruba	1 (0.8)	5 (4.00)		
Fulani	22 (17.6)	5 (4.00)		
Jukun	9 (7.2)	12 (9.6)		
Other Tribes	29 (23.2)	37 (29.6)		
MARITAL STATUS				
			2.016	0.156
Married	125 (100.0)	123 (98.4)		
Single	0 (0.00)	2 (1.6)		
LEVEL OF EDUCATION				
			46.342	< 0.01*
None	16 (12.8)			
Primary	9 (7.2)	0 (0.00)		
Secondary	80 (64.0)	31 (24.8)		
Tertiary	20 (16.0)	48 (38.4)		
		46 (36.8)		
AGE (years)				
			37.922	< 0.01*
18-25	75 (60.0)			
26-30	36 (28.8)	33 (26.4)		
31-35	8 (6.4)	46 (36.8)		
36-40	5 (4.0)	20 (16.0)		
>40	1 (0.8)	26 (20.8)		
		0 (0.00)		
NUMBER OF CHILDREN				
			13.167	< 0.004*
<3	79 (63.2)			
3-5	40 (32.0)	51 (40.8)		
6-8	6 (4.8)	63 (50.4)		
>8	0 (0.00)	10 (8.0)		
		1 (0.8)		

NWM= Non -working mothers WM= Working mothers . Others: Jarawa, Ebira, Sayawa, Alago, Ngas, Magavwul

Table 2: Sociodemographic characteristics of children in both groups

Variable	NWM (%) n=125	WM (%) n=125	χ^2	p-value
Sex distribution			1.28	0.258
Female	58 (46.4)	51 (40.8)		
Male	67 (53.6)	74 (59.2)		
Age group (in months)			16.85	0.001*
0-23	73(58.4)	53 (42.4)		
24-35	28(22.4)	32 (25.6)		
36-47	8 (6.4)	23(18.4)		
48-59	16(12.8)	23(18.4)		

NWM= Non-working mothers WM= Working mothers

Table 3: Association between maternal employment status and child nutritional status

Nutritional indicator	WM (%) n-125	NWM (%) n-125	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Underweight (WAZ)	14 (11.2)	21 (16.8)	0.59 (0.30-1.29)	0.241
Stunting (HAZ)	9 (7.2)	16 (12.8)	0.53 (0.23-1.25)	0.121
Wasting (WHZ)	17(13.6)	26 (20.8)	0.60 (0.32-1.14)	0.118

Reference group: non-working mothers

Adjusted for: maternal age, maternal education, number of children, occupation.

Table 4A: Association between maternal education and child malnutrition among working mothers

Level of education	Underweight AOR (95% CI)	p-value	Stunting AOR (95% CI)	p-value	Wasting AOR (95% CI)	p-value
None	-	-	-	-	-	-
Primary	5.7 (1.4-23.1)	0.015	13.1 (1.5-113.2)	0.019	4.6 (1.5-14.3)	0.008*
Secondary	2.6 (0.7-9.6)	0.149	4.4 (0.5-37.5)	0.175	1.9 (0.7-5.4)	0.221
Tertiary	1.0(ref)	-	1.0 (ref)	-	1.0(ref)	-

Reference group: Tertiary education

Bonferroni correction was applied for multiple comparisons across education levels

Table 4 B: Association between maternal education and child malnutrition among non-working mothers

Level of education	Underweight AOR (95% CI)	p-value	Stunting AOR (95% CI)	p-value	Wasting AOR (95% CI)	p-value
None	13.2 (2.9-60.4)	0.001*	27.8 (3.0-259.1)	0.004*	10.1 (2.8-36.1)	<0.001*
Primary	5.7 (1.4-23.1)	0.015*	13.1 (1.5-113.2)	0.019	4.6 (1.5-14.3)	0.008*
Secondary	2.6 (0.7-9.6)	0.149	4.4 (0.5-37.5)	0.175	1.9 (0.7-5.4)	0.221
Tertiary	1.0 (reference)	-	1.0 (reference)	-	1.0 (reference)	-

Reference group: Tertiary education

Bonferroni correction was applied for multiple comparisons across education levels

Discussion

The mean age of nonworking mothers was 26.8±5.1 years and majority of them had less than three children. This is similar to patterns observed in other Nigerian contexts, where early marriage and limited family planning access contribute to adolescent motherhood.^{10,16} This demographic pattern also aligns with national trends from the National Demographic and Health Survey⁷, where younger mothers in north central region like Plateau State are more likely to be unemployed, increasing vulnerability to poverty-driven malnutrition. In contrast, working mothers were older with more children suggesting delayed family building or economic necessity driving labour participation, similar with southwestern Nigeria data.¹⁷ Higher education among working mother's highlights the role of literacy as a facilitator of employment, which can enable better resource allocation for child health.

Children of non-working mothers had higher malnutrition rates. This challenges the assumption that non-employment provides more time for childcare. This is likely due to unmeasured confounders such as household food security or paternal involvement. These findings are similar with a North Central Nigerian study which links unemployment to poverty-induced wasting,¹⁸ where socio-economic constraints can overshadow the availability of time for better feeding practices unlike NDHS national estimates⁴, possibly because their design captures urban time constraints more robustly, whereas this clinic-based study shows rural-suburban poverty.

Also, the absence of a significant independent association between maternal employment and malnutrition after multivariable adjustment is similar to recent evidence from northern and north-central Nigeria¹⁹, where income from informal, flexible work appears to offset any reduction in direct childcare time. This shows that, in settings dominated by poverty and low literacy, socio-economic constraints often overshadow the availability of time for optimal feeding practices, whereas the additional household income from maternal work can mitigate food insecurity.

Maternal literacy was a protective factor in this study against malnutrition, with having secondary/tertiary education reducing underweight, stunting, and wasting risks. This favorable outcome is most likely due to enhanced knowledge of feeding practices and dietary diversity. The effect was increased in working mothers, where literacy synergizes with income to reduce time barriers. This is in contrasts to non-working mothers where lower literacy put their children to be more vulnerable to risks of malnutrition.

This is similar to a 2023 analysis of Demographic and Health Survey Data from Ghana, Nigeria and Cote d'Ivoire which showed that children of mothers with no formal education had the highest odds of malnutrition, with the risk declining with each additional level of schooling.^{13, 20} A 2021 analysis of 31 sub-Saharan African countries similarly identified maternal education as one of the strongest modifiable determinants of adverse nutritional outcomes.²¹ Unlike a study on stunting

in under-fives attending immunization clinics in Jos North LGA where a third of the children were stunted²², our study had lower levels of stunting. This may likely be a reflection of differences in clinic populations despite similar facility-based design in Plateau state.

The study has limitations due to the consecutive sampling which was used for feasibility but it may introduce selection bias by excluding non-clinic attendees and a cross sectional study design which does not allow the establishment of temporality or causality. The results of the study have direct program implications for Plateau State and similar Nigerian communities because accelerating girls' education and adult female literacy programs remain the highest-leverage, long-term strategy for reducing malnutrition.

Conclusion

Maternal literacy, not employment per se, is the primary driver of child nutritional status in this study. Nutrition and child-health programs should therefore deliberately prioritize mothers with little or no formal education and households with lower income with conditional cash transfers and micronutrient supplementation. Routine child-health services, including immunization clinics and growth-monitoring sessions, should be strengthened and used as platforms to deliver targeted support to the most disadvantaged groups. For working mothers, workplace policies such as subsidized childcare and breastfeeding facilities could mitigate time constraints and improve nutritional status. Future longitudinal research is recommended to clarify the pathways linking socioeconomic factors to child nutritional outcomes. Integrating such equity-focused actions into existing primary health-care and community systems provides a practical and sustainable strategy to reduce child undernutrition in Nigeria.

Declarations

No conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

M. N. G. conceptualized, collected/analyzed data, wrote manuscript, A. F. S. reviewed the methodology/data analysis and D. M. E. reviewed the literature. All authors finalized and approved the manuscript.

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